

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style.

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.)
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example; 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 1 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts: seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (%; infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Genetic behavior of an unstable locus for plant height in rice

M. N. Shrivastava and D. V. Seshu, International Rice Research Institute

A spontaneous semidwarf mutant (77.5 cm) was isolated from the bulk population of Kalimoonch 64, a tall (112.0 cm), scented, and photoperiod-sensitive rice variety from Madhya Pradesh, India. In general, the mutant has qualitative and quantitative characters similar to those of its parent except for reduced plant height. But visual observations over several seasons indicated instability of plant height.

Several panicles were strictly selfed through bagging during the 1979 dry season at Los Baños, Philippines. Selfed seeds were planted in wooden boxes containing thoroughly ground and finely sieved soil in the greenhouse. Seedlings were transplanted as single panicle progeny at 30- × 30-cm spacing in a well-puddled field. Frequency of tall revertants was recorded and these were harvested separately. True breeding lines were selfed and planted in individual panicle rows the next season.

Frequency of back mutations varied from 1.04% to 1.22% (Table 1). All 7 individual revertants harvested during the 1979 wet season segregated for plant

height during subsequent plantings, indicating a single allele reversion. With only 20 plants/progeny, ratios could not be worked out but these observations indicate instability of the mutant at gene or possibly chromosome level.

A few additional characteristics, apiculus and husk color, awning, length and breadth of grains, and days to maturity, mutated occasionally. One photoperiod-insensitive early mutant has been isolated. All mutations are under further study.

The F₁ hybrids of the mutant with other semidwarf cultivars such as IR42 and IR38 (carrying *Dee-geo-woo-gen* gene), Double dwarf 3 (a Calrose mutant from California), and Culture 854 (Baok derivative from India) were all tall, indicating that the dwarfing gene of the mutant is nonallelic with those of the other semidwarfs (Table 2).

The F₁ hybrids of the mutant with IR42 and IR38 showed 30 to 70% sterility but no detectable abnormality in meiosis. The F₂ planted during the 1980 dry season exhibited a unimodal normal distribution, indicating a polygenic inheritance.

Further studies are under way to understand the genetic behavior of the mutant and the phenomenon of instability. ■

Table 1. Frequency of mutation for tall plant stature in selfed progeny of Kalimoonch dwarf mutant at IRRI.

Season	Progeny grown (no.)	Total plants (no.)	Revertants	
			No.	%
1979 dry	—	385	4	1.04
1979 wet	38	570	7	1.22
1980 dry	48	2400	29	1.21

Table 2. Plant height of parents and F₁ hybrids in allelic studies at IRRI.

Cultivar	Height (cm)	Hybrid	Height (cm)
Kalimoonch 64 (tall parent)	112.0	Kalimoonch mutant/IR42	111.0
Kalimoonch dwarf mutant	55.7	Kalimoonch mutant/IR38	115.0
IR42	88.2	Kalimoonch mutant/Culture 854	122.0
IR38	86.3	Kalimoonch mutant/Double dwarf 3	126.8
Culture 854	73.5		
Double dwarf 3	65.0		